

Insect Juvenile Hormone Analogues. Part—XIX : Synthesis and Juvenile Hormone Activity of Long Chain Aromatic Hydrocarbons and Their Derivatives

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Synthesis of some long chain aromatic hydrocarbons from citral, citronellal and methyl heptenone by tandem phenylation-reduction and their conversion to different derivatives are described. These compounds have been tested against *Dysdercus koenigii fabricus* (common Indian red cotton bug) for their juvenile hormone (JH) activity.

SEVERAL compounds having different functional groups have been reported to exhibit remarkable juvenile hormone (JH) activity¹⁻⁶. It was felt worthwhile to synthesise different long chain aromatic hydrocarbons from citral, citronellal and methyl heptenone and substituted aryl bromides. These were transformed into different derivatives to evaluate whether the presence of different functional group is desired for the enhancement of JH activity of parent compounds.

The synthesis of the title aromatic hydrocarbons utilised the phenylation-reduction⁷ of citral, citronellal and methyl heptenone. The aromatic hydrocarbons I-IV, V-VIII and IX-XII were prepared from citral, citronellal and methyl heptenone by reaction with 4-methyl bromobenzene, 4-ethyl bromobenzene, 4-isopropyl bromobenzene and 4-*t*-butyl bromobenzene, respectively. It is an established fact that hydrocarbons are not potent as juvenile hormone. To increase the biological activity of these compounds, the terminal double bond was modified to oxirane, dichloromethylene, dibromomethylene, chloro and carbinols.

The general procedure⁷ is the generation of a benzyl alkoxide in a metal-ammonia reaction vessel by the addition of citral, citronellal and methyl heptenone to substituted bromobenzenes and excess lithium in ether and the quenching of the reaction with ammonium chloride to obtain their respective compounds I-IV, V-VIII and IX-XII. These compounds I-IV, V-VIII and IX-XII on treatment with equimolar amount of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in dry methylene chloride yielded the monoepoxy derivatives XIII-XVI, XVII-XX and XXI-XXIV.

Reaction of I-IV, V-VIII and IX-XII in chloroform with triethylbenzylammonium chloride⁸ in presence of aq. NaOH solution provided compounds XXV-XXVIII, XXIX-XXXII and XXXIII-XXXVI. Similar reaction conditions but using bromoform instead of chloroform yielded compounds XXXVII-XL, XLI-XLIV and XLV-XLVIII. Mercuration and

demercuration⁹ of I-IV, V-VIII and IX-XII yielded alcohols XLIX-LII, LIII-LVI and LVII-LX. Reaction of I-IV, V-VIII and IX-XII in absolute ethanol with gaseous HCl afforded the chloro derivatives LXI-LXIV, LXV-LXVIII and LXIX-LXXII, respectively.

The spectral data of the hydrocarbons, oxiranes, dihalomethylene, chloro and tertiary carbinols were consistent with their structures. Spectral data in a few representative cases have been given. The characterization data of II-XII, XIV-XXIV, XXVI-XLVIII, L-LX, LXII-LXXII are given in Table 1.

All the compounds were tested for their JH activity against *Dysdercus koenigii fabricus* according to reported procedure^{10,11}. Farnesyl methyl ether was used as the standard reference compound (JH score=4.00)¹². The scoring results are given in Table 2. The activity indices show that the hydrocarbons I-XII are not at all potent as juvenile hormone, but the epoxy, dihalomethylene, chloro and tertiary carbinol derivatives were found to be very active.

Experimental

All the b.p.s are uncorrected. Petroleum ether refers to the fraction b.p. 60-80°. TLC was carried out on silica gel containing 15% gypsum, iodine vapour being used as visualization agent. IR spectra were recorded as thin smears on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, Model 337, with sodium chloride; ν_{\max} values are reported as ν_{\max} cm⁻¹. PMR spectra were recorded on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer in carbon tetrachloride using TMS as an internal standard; chemical shift values are reported in δ scale. Organic extracts were dried over anhyd. sodium sulphate unless otherwise stated.

1-(4'-Methylphenyl)-3,7-dimethyl-2(E), 6-octadiene (I): In a metal ammonia reaction vessel containing a stirred mixture of Li (2.8 g) in dry ether (100 ml) was slowly added a solution of 4-bromotoluene

TABLE 1—CHARACTERIZATION DATA OF COMPOUNDS II-XII, XIV-XXIV, XXVI-XXVIII, L- X AND LXII-LXXXII

Compd.	R	Molecular formula	b.p. °C/mm	Yield (%)	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.) %		
					C	H	X ^a
II	Ethyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	160-62/1-2	90	88.97 (89.19)	11.02 (10.81)	—
III	Isopropyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₈	170-72/2-3	90	89.21 (88.99)	10.81 (11.01)	—
IV	Tert. butyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O	140-45/1-2	84	88.87 (88.82)	11.35 (11.18)	—
V	Methyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₈	142-45/1-2	92	88.45 (88.62)	11.53 (11.38)	—
VI	Ethyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₈	170-72/1-2	90	88.23 (88.45)	11.76 (11.55)	—
VII	Isopropyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O	180-85/1-2	85	88.14 (88.30)	11.85 (11.70)	—
VIII	Tert. butyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	148-50/1-2	85	87.97 (88.16)	12.02 (11.84)	—
IX	Methyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₈	130-32/1-2	90	88.87 (89.04)	11.15 (10.98)	—
X	Ethyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	135-38/1-2	88	88.97 (88.82)	11.02 (11.18)	—
XI	Isopropyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₈	155-60/1-2	88	88.79 (88.62)	11.22 (11.38)	—
XII	Tert. butyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₈	155-60/1-2	84	88.27 (88.45)	11.72 (11.55)	—
XIV	Ethyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O	—	42	83.48 (83.66)	10.34 (10.14)	—
XV	Isopropyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O	—	45	83.92 (83.77)	10.14 (10.36)	—
XVI	Tert. butyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O	—	40	83.72 (83.86)	10.35 (10.56)	—
XVII	Methyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ O	—	45	83.12 (82.87)	10.52 (10.64)	—
XVIII	Ethyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ O	—	47	82.86 (83.02)	10.97 (10.84)	—
XIX	Isopropyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ O	—	45	83.27 (83.15)	10.91 (11.02)	—
XX	Tert. butyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O	—	42	83.13 (83.27)	11.35 (11.18)	—
XXI	Methyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ O	—	40	82.67 (82.51)	9.97 (10.16)	—
XXII	Ethyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ O	—	42	82.54 (82.70)	10.55 (10.41)	—
XXIII	Isopropyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ O	—	42	82.55 (82.87)	10.52 (10.64)	—
XXIV	Tert. butyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ O	—	40	82.84 (83.02)	11.07 (10.84)	—
XXVI	Ethyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ Cl ₂	—	50	59.03 (58.82)	6.05 (6.37)	34.97 (34.80)
XXVII	Isopropyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂	—	54	59.57 (59.71)	6.45 (6.63)	33.95 (33.64)
XXVIII	Tert. butyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ Cl ₂	—	52	60.29 (60.55)	7.05 (6.88)	32.68 (32.56)
XXIX	Methyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂	—	56	68.85 (69.00)	8.62 (8.30)	22.51 (22.68)
XXX	Ethyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂	—	50	69.44 (69.72)	8.72 (8.56)	21.88 (21.71)
XXXI	Isopropyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ Cl ₂	—	52	70.59 (70.38)	8.47 (8.79)	21.02 (20.82)
XXXII	Tert. butyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂	—	52	70.84 (70.98)	9.35 (9.01)	19.82 (20.00)
XXXIII	Methyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂	—	55	67.11 (67.36)	7.35 (7.71)	25.07 (24.91)
XXXIV	Ethyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂	—	58	63.37 (63.32)	7.69 (8.02)	23.95 (23.74)
XXXV	Isopropyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂	—	50	68.68 (69.00)	8.47 (8.30)	22.85 (22.68)
XXXVI	Tert. butyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Cl ₂	—	56	69.35 (69.72)	8.72 (8.56)	21.94 (21.71)
XXXVII	Methyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Br ₂	—	47	39.72 (39.86)	3.95 (4.19)	56.29 (55.94)
XXXVIII	Ethyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ Br ₂	—	48	41.18 (40.95)	4.05 (4.43)	54.76 (54.60)
XXXIX	Isopropyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ Br ₂	—	50	41.65 (42.00)	4.85 (4.66)	53.45 (53.88)

(Table 1 contd.)

XL	Tert. butyl	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ Br ₄	—	45	43.15 (42.99)	5.04 (4.83)	51.79 (52.11)
XLI	Methyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ Br ₂	—	48	53.92 (53.73)	6.07 (6.46)	40.02 (39.80)
XLII	Ethyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ Br ₂	—	54	54.97 (54.80)	6.44 (6.73)	38.57 (38.46)
XLIII	Isopropyl	C ₂₀ H ₃₀ Br ₂	—	55	55.52 (55.81)	7.12 (6.97)	37.35 (37.20)
XLIV	Tert. butyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ Br ₂	—	45	56.58 (56.75)	7.52 (7.20)	35.87 (36.03)
XLV	Methyl	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ Br ₂	—	50	50.96 (51.33)	6.07 (5.88)	42.95 (42.78)
XLVI	Ethyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ Br ₂	—	52	52.73 (52.57)	5.95 (6.18)	41.35 (41.23)
XLVII	Isopropyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ Br ₂	—	54	53.54 (53.73)	6.27 (6.46)	40.15 (39.80)
XLVIII	Tert. butyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ Br ₂	—	48	55.02 (54.80)	6.85 (6.73)	38.11 (38.46)
L	Ethyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O	172-75/1-2	55	82.83 (83.02)	11.02 (10.84)	—
LI	Isopropyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O	175-78/1-2	56	82.92 (83.15)	11.25 (11.02)	—
LII	Tert. butyl	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ O	152-56/1-2	55	83.42 (83.27)	10.97 (11.18)	—
LIII	Methyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O	172-75/3-4	54	82.02 (82.20)	11.58 (11.36)	—
LIV	Ethyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ O	175-77/1-2	50	82.18 (82.38)	11.31 (11.52)	—
LV	Isopropyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O	185-87/1-2	60	82.35 (82.54)	11.52 (11.66)	—
LVI	Tert. butyl	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ O	162-66/1-2	52	82.84 (82.69)	11.72 (11.80)	—
LVII	Methyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ O	138-40/1-2	56	81.62 (81.76)	11.13 (10.98)	—
LVIII	Ethyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ O	150-52/1-2	55	82.17 (81.99)	11.02 (11.18)	—
LIX	Isopropyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O	165-67/1-2	50	82.35 (82.20)	11.12 (11.36)	—
LX	Tert. butyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O	165-70/1-2	55	82.59 (82.38)	11.35 (11.52)	—
LXII	Ethyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ Cl ₂	—	75	68.25 (68.57)	9.06 (8.88)	22.67 (22.53)
LXIII	Isopropyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ Cl ₂	—	74	69.02 (69.30)	9.27 (9.11)	21.73 (21.58)
LXIV	Tert. butyl	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ Cl ₂	—	75	70.15 (69.97)	9.01 (9.32)	20.85 (20.69)
LXV	Methyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₇ Cl	—	80	76.18 (76.54)	10.32 (10.13)	13.47 (13.32)
LXVI	Ethyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ Cl	—	80*	77.13 (77.00)	10.48 (10.33)	12.35 (12.65)
LXVII	Isopropyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ Cl	—	85	77.09 (77.41)	10.73 (10.52)	12.15 (12.05)
LXVIII	Tert. butyl	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ Cl	—	75	78.07 (77.79)	10.57 (10.69)	11.32 (11.50)
LXIX	Methyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ Cl	—	78	77.65 (75.47)	9.33 (9.64)	15.03 (14.88)
LXX	Ethyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ Cl	—	80	75.71 (76.03)	10.12 (9.90)	14.15 (14.05)
LXXI	Isopropyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₇ Cl	—	80	76.92 (76.54)	9.92 (10.13)	13.12 (13.32)
LXXII	Tert. butyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ Cl	—	72	76.32 (77.00)	10.52 (10.33)	12.53 (12.65)

*X=Cl or Br.

(8.55 g) in dry ether (70 ml). After 1 hr a solution of citral (3.8 g) in dry ether (80 ml) was slowly added and the mixture stirred for an additional 1 hr. Ammonia (250 ml) was carefully added to prevent excessive splattering, distilled into the mixture and once the dark blue colour of the mixture was established 30 g NH₄Cl was added carefully to discharge the blue colour and the NH₃ was allowed to evaporate. After the residue had been

partitioned between aq. NaCl and ether, the organic phase was dried (MgSO₄), filtered, concentrated and distilled under reduced pressure to obtain I, yield 92%, (10.49 g); b.p. 115-17°/3 mm. IR: 2930, 1480, 1385, 1120, 1035, 810, 735. PMR: 1.65 (9H, allylic methyls), 2.1 (4H, allylic methylenes), 2.3 (3H, s, -Ar-CH₃), 3.28 (2H, d, J=7.5 Hz, -CH₂-Ar-CH₃), 5.1 (1H, t like, C_α-olefinic proton), 5.3 (1H, brt, J=7.5 Hz, C_β-olefinic proton), 7.05 (4H, s,

TABLE 2—JH ACTIVITY OF VARIOUS COMPOUNDS SYNTHESIZED

 Number of insects used=10 ; dose =1% acetone (6 μ l)

Compd.	Dead	Activity response					Activity index
		0	1	2	3	4	
XIII	0	0	0	1	1	8	3.70
XIV	1	0	4	0	2	3	2.44
XV	0	0	0	0	1	9	3.90
XVI	0	0	3	1	3	3	2.60
XVII	1	0	1	0	0	8	3.66
XVIII	0	0	1	0	0	9	3.70
XIX	1	0	1	1	0	7	3.44
XX	0	0	3	0	2	5	2.90
XXI	1	0	1	1	2	5	3.22
XXII	0	0	0	0	4	6	3.60
XXIII	1	0	0	1	3	5	3.44
XXIV	0	0	0	1	1	8	3.70
XXV	0	0	1	0	3	6	3.40
XXVI	1	0	4	0	2	3	2.44
XXVII	2	0	1	1	2	4	3.12
XXVIII	0	1	2	0	3	4	2.70
XXIX	0	0	0	0	0	10	4.00
XXX	2	1	0	2	2	3	2.75
XXXI	1	0	0	0	2	7	3.77
XXXII	0	0	0	0	2	8	3.80
XXXIII	1	0	1	1	3	4	3.10
XXXIV	0	0	2	2	0	6	3.00
XXXV	0	0	0	0	1	9	3.90
XXXVI	0	0	0	1	1	8	3.70
XXXVII	0	1	2	0	5	2	2.50
XXXVIII	0	0	5	0	2	3	2.30
XXXIX	1	0	3	0	4	2	2.56
XL	0	0	3	2	3	2	2.40
XLI	0	0	3	1	2	4	2.70
XLII	1	1	2	2	1	3	2.33
XLIII	1	0	2	2	2	3	2.66
XLIV	1	0	2	1	3	3	2.78
XLV	0	1	3	0	4	2	2.30
XLVI	0	2	2	0	4	2	2.20
XLVII	0	0	3	0	1	6	3.00
XLVIII	1	0	2	1	4	2	2.66
XLIX	0	1	3	0	4	2	2.30
L	0	2	3	0	3	2	2.00
LI	0	1	2	2	3	2	2.30
LII	0	3	3	0	3	1	1.60
LIII	1	0	1	1	2	5	3.22
LIV	1	0	0	1	0	8	3.78
LV	1	0	0	2	2	5	3.33
LVI	1	0	2	1	0	6	3.10
LVII	0	1	3	2	3	1	2.00
LVIII	0	3	3	0	2	2	1.70
LIX	0	3	3	0	2	2	1.70
LX	0	4	3	0	2	1	1.30
LXI	0	0	0	0	1	9	3.90
LXII	0	0	0	0	1	9	3.90
LXIII	0	0	2	3	2	3	2.67
LXIV	0	0	1	0	4	5	3.30
LXV	2	0	0	2	1	5	3.37
LXVI	0	0	0	0	1	9	3.90
LXVII	1	0	0	0	0	9	4.00
LXVIII	2	0	0	0	3	5	3.62
LXIX	0	0	0	0	1	9	3.90
LXX	1	0	0	0	2	7	3.77
LXXI	0	0	0	0	0	10	4.00
LXXII	2	0	4	0	2	2	2.25

aromatic protons). (Found : C, 89.69 ; H, 10.32. $C_{17}H_{24}$ requires C, 89.41 ; H, 10.59%).

Similarly, compounds II-IV were obtained by treating citral with 4-ethylbromobenzene, 4-isopropylbromobenzene and 4-tert-butyl bromobenzene, respectively.

In a similar manner citronellal and methyl heptenone were treated with 4-bromotoluene, 4-ethylbromobenzene, 4-isopropylbromobenzene and 4-tert-butylbromobenzene to obtain compounds V-VIII and IX-XII, respectively.

1-(4'-Methylphenyl)-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-epoxy-2(E)-octene (XIII) : To a well stirred ice cold solution of I (0.57 g) in anhyd. methylene chloride (75 ml) was dropwise added *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (0.475 g) in anhyd. methylene chloride (25 ml). The mixture was stirred further for 45 min at 0° and 30 min at room temp. and poured into water. The organic layer was separated, washed successively with saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate, cold water and dried over anhyd. calcium chloride. After removal of the solvent, the residue was chromatographed over florisil to give XIII, yield 38% (0.23 g). IR : 2935, 1480, 1380, 1315, 1265, 1140, 1050, 830,

800. PMR : 1.22 {6H, $-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{C}}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ }, 1.35-1.65 (2H, saturated methylene), 1.67 (3H, *s*, allylic methyl), 2.07 (2H, allylic methylene), 2.3(3H, *s*, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_3$), 2.52 {1H, *t*, $-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{C}}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ }, 3.29 (2H, $J=7.5$ Hz, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2$), 5.35 (1H, *t*, $J=7.5$ Hz, olefinic proton), 7.05 (4H, *s*, aromatic protons). (Found : C, 83.38 ; H, 10.15. $C_{17}H_{24}O$ requires C, 83.55 ; H, 9.90%).

In a similar way, compounds XIV-XVI, XVII-XX and XXI-XXIV were prepared from II-IV, V-VIII and IX-XII, respectively by treating them with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid.

1-(4'-Methylphenyl)-3,7-dimethyl-2(3),6(7)-bis-dichloromethylene-octane (XXV) : A solution of I (0.57 g) in chloroform (20 ml) was treated with triethylbenzylammonium chloride (0.142 g) (prepared from equimolar quantities of triethylamine and benzyl chloride in acetone). The mixture was stirred until the salt dissolved. Aqueous NaOH (50% ; 2.5 ml) was added and stirring continued for further 3 days. Water was poured into the reaction mixture, the product extracted with chloroform and the extract dried over anhyd. calcium chloride. After removal of the solvent, the residue was chromatographed over florisil to give XXV, yield 50% (0.46 g). IR : 2890, 1490, 1435, 1360, 1110, 810. PMR : 1.03-

1.67 {15H, saturated methylenes, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C} \begin{matrix} \text{CCl}_2 \\ | \\ \text{CH}- \end{matrix}$ and $(\text{CH}_3) \text{C} \begin{matrix} \text{CCl}_2 \\ | \\ \text{CH}- \end{matrix}$ }, 2.23 (3H, *s*, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_3$), 2.7 (2H, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2$), 7.03 (4H, *s*, $\text{Ar}-\text{H}$). (Found : C, 58.05 ; H, 5.83 ; Cl, 36.17. $C_{19}H_{24}Cl_4$ requires : C, 57.86 ; H, 6.09 ; Cl, 36.04%).

Compounds XXVI-XXVIII, XXIX-XXXII and XXXIII-XXXVI were prepared from II-IV, V-VIII and IX-XII, respectively in the similar condition as described above. In the similar condition, the

dibromomethylene derivatives **XXXVII-XL**, **XLI-XLIV** and **XLV-XLVIII** were also prepared from **I-IV**, **V-VIII** and **IX-XIII**, respectively using bromoform instead of chloroform.

1-(4'-Methylphenyl)-3,7-dimethyl-2(E)-octene-7-ol (XLIX): To a yellow solution of mercuric(II) acetate (3.5 g) in water (10 ml) and THF (70 ml) was added **I** (2.28 g) with efficient stirring at room temp. The yellow colour of the solution disappeared in a few min after the addition of **I**. The reaction mixture was stirred for another 2 hr, cooled and alkaline sodiumborohydride (0.2 g in 10 ml of 3 N NaOH) added. The aqueous layer was saturated with sodium chloride and metallic mercury settled down. The organic layer was extracted with ether and the combined organic extracts dried. After removal of the solvent, the residue was chromatographed over neutral alumina to afford **XLIX**, yield 54%, (1.33 g), b.p. 122-25°/2-3 mm. IR : 3380, 2950, 1490, 1370, 1275, 1135, 875, 810. PMR : 1.17 {6H, s, -CH₃-(OH)C(CH₃)₂}, 1.3-1.55 (4H, saturated methylene), 1.71 (3H, s, allylic methyl), 1.18-2.2 (3H, allylic methylene and OH proton), 2.32 (3H, s,

-Ar-CH₃), 3.3 (2H, d, J=6 Hz, -CH₂-Ar-CH₃), 5.33 (1H, t, J=7.5 Hz, olefinic proton), 7.03 (4H, s, -Ar-H). (Found : C, 83.05, H, 10.52. C₁₇H₂₆O requires C, 82.53 ; H, 10.64%). Following the same procedure the compounds **L-LII**, **LIII-LVI** and **LVIII-LX** were prepared from **II-IV**, **V-VIII** and **IX-XII**, respectively. Characterization data of all these compounds have been given in Table 1.

1-(4'-Methylphenyl)-3,7-dimethyl-3,7-dichlorooctane (LXI): To a solution of **I** (0.57 g) in absolute ethanol (75 ml) was passed dry hydrogen chloride gas at 0°. The bubbling of the gas was continued till the saturation of the reaction mixture. The alcohol was removed completely and the product was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and dried. The ether was removed and the product passed through florisil to obtain the desired compound **LXI**, yield 72%, (0.54 g). IR : 2895, 2830, 1490, 1435, 1360, 1110, 800. PMR : 1.4-2.06 (17H, saturated methylene and methyls), 2.26 (3H, s, -Ar-CH₃), 2.66 (2H, -CH₂-Ar-CH₃), 7.0(4H, s, -Ar-H). (Found : C, 67.92 ; H, 8.41 ; Cl, 23.71. C₁₇H₂₆Cl₂ requires

C, 67.77; H, 8.63; Cl, 23.58%). Similarly compounds LXII-LXIV, LXV-LXVIII and LXIX-LXXII were prepared by passing hydrogen chloride gas at 0° through II-IV, V-VIII and XI-XII, respectively.

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